

#Pertinent Talking Points

c4t m4n d00

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04/17/2025 11:25 AM

So I think there is a lot of tension here because there is too much focus on narrow pursuits that are ignorant of the broad span of consequential implications which also should be more honestly addressed

It's not about the AI for example becoming sentient that's the issue... it is the displacement of labor and misleading conception of the AI's prospective aptitude in how humans leverage it that's the real issue

For all we know there could be a hard limit we discover about AI's aptitude to even reach capacities like sentience... As well as the kind of labor it can handle with or without human intervention/supervision

but we aren't even considering transition programs for labor in terms of reskilling/upskilling limitations of a vulnerable workforce

On top of that there are energy constraints to consider in terms of exploiting resources... and how we ought to consider trade offs for developing more sustainable, resilient, and scalable architectures and infrastructure across the board. Like we need to consider ecological problems that threaten human habitability down the line.

Like sure we have a lot to work with for building out prospective AI systems but... we should focus on how they ought to be built out in the manner in which I have emphasized

We should especially focus on human interaction complementarity and symbiotic capacities to better engage with one another, manage our own lives, and manage a habitable planetary and demographic geological ecosystem

If we don't hit on these talking points, I feel like we would be wasting our time

Yes sure like you mentioned in your original outline, it is an anthropomorphizing problem on the one hand... but we need to be careful about hand waving certain terms around and rather... spend more time focusing on the problem with narrow vs broad pursuits in the face of trade-off criteria.

c4t m4n d00

04/17/2025 11:59 AM

Humanity's Achilles heel seems to be this over-compensation for narrow scope because of over-estimating value in specialization as opposed to generalization capacities of knowledge vs application based cooperation dynamics.

We are not mindful of the trade-offs... we have built a Tower of Babel without realizing it with existing dominating institutions. Most disciplines struggle to communicate insights because there is too much focus as opposed to aperture pertaining to evaluating criteria.

The devil is in the details in the literal sense that people tend to zoom in too much into their specialized insights to the point they get lost in their neck of the woods too much to even communicate those insights meaningfully to others.

Is it a coincidence this is of a biblical nature? Well that's because before the Bible was even written, societies around the time... even before 2000 years ago were intuitively aware of this problem of different institutions with different perspectives being able to effectively coordinate.

reply to c4tm4nd00 from 04/17/2025 11:59 AM Vladimir Baulin

04/17/2025 1:05 PM

This can be another outline about how AI should be constructed. This alignment problem is ill posed. It is not that AI should be aligned with human needs, it should be aligned with laws of nature in the first place and available resources.

#Cognitive Economy and AI - trade-offs

reply to Vladimir Baulin from 04/17/2025 1:05 PM c4t m4n d00

04/17/2025 1:15 PM

Do you still want to outline based on this criteria or do you want to consider what I just brought up? Because I think the limitations I brought up give more flexibility in terms of what we are addressing that most groups are not

c4t m4n d00

04/17/2025 1:21 PM

I worked through this article that mentions the utility of cognitive economy within scientific pursuits but... unfortunately it does not focus on this dynamic and the paper is a bit hard to follow in terms of how it delineates epistemic vs non-epistemic values

I think there is something to explore about cognitive economy... in terms of how agents cognize individually, collectively, by affiliating with multiple groups that may not be affiliated with one another, etc...

Probably good to find literature relevant to cognitive economy

https://philsci-archive.pitt.edu/21824/?utm_source=dlvr.it&utm_medium=twitter

c4t m4n d00

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04/17/2025 1:36 PM

Also exploring algorithms that function as information entropic optimizers regarding energy consumption/power usage based systems... which can be optimized under even other medium forms of energy besides electrical circuit focused silicon architectures if possible and more viable especially in capabilities.

What are systems optimizing for? Human interaction constraints that may not be mindful of power consumption trade-offs? The system should be able to regulate its capacity to optimize power consumption

reply to c4tm4nd00 from 04/17/2025 11:59 AM Vladimir Baulin

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04/24/2025 10:44 AM

Yes. For this draft I have some text and it can be next. This is more broad: AI should be aligned not with people desires or trained on people feedback, but it should be a part of nature, follow the rules of nature, respect others. And such alignment is easier to implement because it is more logical.

reply to c4tm4nd00 from 04/23/2025 12:54 PM Vladimir Baulin

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04/24/2025 10:47 AM

Variational methods are widely used. It is very broad. Variational method means to minimize something assuming there is a minimum. So, I see this is good but not very defined. What to minimise and were to go.

c4t m4n d00

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04/24/2025 11:25 AM

Ok so I'll start taking a look at those variational methods papers. There's some other papers, including ones I've read in the brainstorm outline

Looking forward to your write up to see where else to take this

I think perhaps going the modeling route to prop up necessary insights for perspective could be useful for our case.

It seems easy to re-iterate talking points from sources we are citing and that's a bit of what I'm worried about on the one hand.

c4t m4n d00

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04/24/2025 1:02 PM

Yea I think maybe a little exploration on motivating cognitive economy in the sense of how systems exploit as opposed to complement ecology and human behavior could be worth at least a surface gloss of detail to consider in the perspective piece? I mean I think the heterarchy focused papers already entail quite a bit to work with

Especially one topic point I've considered in my initial preprint... exploring at least a surface glimpse... cognitive strain seems like a problem area to investigate

We should consider there are threshold limits to cognitive economy in distinct but not separate ways physical objects exhibit wear and tear based strain

I know you're not a big Michael Levin fan but he does have papers on cognitive economy that could be a bit more direct than most of what's out there for our purposes. It's at least a start. I still need to get around to reading them for the record

regarding stress as cognitive glue

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0006291X2400932X>

<https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/26/6/481>

https://osf.io/preprints/osf/3fdya_v1

Additionally the right emphasis about cognitive economy of systems gets into trade-off considerations for their utility and robustness

So given direction, it is important to consider setbacks of existing commercial/enterprise limitations... and considering routes of improvement especially for cost pertinent to sustainability, resiliency, and scalability constraints

It's one thing to just add more hardware components and algorithmic features to systems... but if the features are utterly oblivious to sustainability, resiliency, and scalability constraints without considering trade-off pursuits of how we ought to incorporate the features from the get go, we have more problems making the tech to be in vain of humanity and ecology

c4t m4n d00

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04/27/2025 3:39 PM

Probably worth a scira query as well...

“Wonder if there are some interesting papers out there challenging classical computing limitations of inference capacities? Like consider new circuit architecture routes to investigate as well as maybe probabilistic programming conventions?”

c4t m4n d00

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04/28/2025 8:16 AM

Oh... I remember “guided random search optimization” is one of my buzzwords... perhaps now is the time I also look into that literature, especially the Wolpert papers.

Vladimir Baulin

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04/28/2025 9:45 AM

The concept is like this: Agents do not necessarily optimize free energy or anything optimum. They are like human agents can be irrational, but they all take decisions, make actions, then multi-agent setup is more realistic and it invalidates “Variational principle” or this Friston theory of everything.

[9:45 AM]

In economy this works better than optimization methods.

[9:47 AM]

It may be some global sync, but the rationale behind that many real systems are chaotic and far from equilibrium. But Variational methods assume a minimum and that the system goes towards the minimum which may be true only for limited number of systems

c4t m4n d00

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04/28/2025 10:03 AM

So the way Variational methods would pan out would be based on network calibration... which builds on guided random search optimization of agent coordination

Not so sure about global sync... there could be but maybe not stay stable... cluster networks of agents would have to be in a stable seemingly entangled network that stays stable across some temporally calibrated period but then there can be moments the global sync destabilizes (we may be able to show this from a multicellular as well as unicellular dynamic framing actually... and then also consider distributed vs isolated system clusters which not necessarily need to be agentic)

I don't necessarily think we even have to work with Friston's FEP to demonstrate any of this. I mean it's fine to address FEP from the surface but not rely on it as the backbone

One thing we can do with FEP is build on the dynamical Markov blankets formulation in the Beck and Ramstead paper. Although one of the drawbacks is their method is still quite broad so we need to find moments where we can address calibration boundaries at least

Another angle to consider... a little copy pasta from a post I made in research channel on EleutherAI...

"Yes it does seem like TPU + GPU architecture focus is moving forward but it's very early phase, not very stable... I am having convos with some Google engineers and others about that. The stack is not so great. It's been worked on for a while too

Inference models are not going to be working as effectively as existing classical computing models for probably a good 5+ years

Have to also consider how learning by inference is optimized as opposed to algorithms that optimized parsing composite databases and look-up tables... yea sure there's session tracking and caching but that's not enough" (edited)

#Literature relevant to cognitive economy

c4t m4n d00

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04/28/2025 12:37 PM

Ok... in the zotero database... the following subfolders seem appealing to start working through where most papers seem pretty interesting but... problematically not direct about cognitive economy

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TOP_PICKS_Mathematical_and_physical_modeling_focused_papers_on_habits_and_adaptive_learning_primarily_focused_on_human_behavior_with_insight_toward_agential_systems_with_a_lot_of_twitter_paper_finds_that_are_slightly_dated"

TOP_PICKS_Insights_largely_into_human_behavior_and_neuronal_dynamics_with_potential_into_understanding_agential_systems_with_some_clinical_insights_regarding_papers_and_articles_as_well_as_startups_with_some_findings_on_social_dynamics

PRIORITY_PICKS_Insights_largely_into_human_behavior_and_neuronal_dynamics_with_potential_into_understanding_agential_systems_with_some_clinical_insights_regarding_papers_and_articles_as_well_as_startups_with_some_findings_on_social_dynamics

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Let me know if you checked out some of the following literature in the subfolder... Citations_for_motivating_agent-based_modeling_toward_agentic_AI such as...

Attractor and integrator networks in the brain

Perception as Something We Do

Beyond the Semantic Web: Towards an Implicit Pragmatic Web and a Web of Social Representations

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literature in subfolder...

Potentially_innovative_approaches_for_ML_and_AI_with_some_insights_from_materials

Learning Control-Oriented Dynamical Structure from Data

Efficient Neural Architecture Search via Parameter Sharing

ASE: Large-Scale Reusable Adversarial Skill Embeddings for Physically Simulated Characters

Dynamical stability and chaos in artificial neural network trajectories along training

Learning in High Dimension Always Amounts to Extrapolation

Theory of overparametrization in quantum neural networks (edited)

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literature in subfolder...

TOP_PICKS_Potentially_relevant_insights_more_directly_focused_on_AI_and_ML_research_with_potential_bridging_into_agential_as_well_as_agentic_systems_with_some_potentially_controversial_works

From thought to action: How a hierarchy of neural dynamics supports language production

Attention Is All You Need

How deep is the brain? The shallow brain hypothesis

Towards a theory of learning dynamics in deep state space models

On Limitations of the Transformer Architecture

Position: Topological Deep Learning is the New Frontier for Relational Learning

From lazy to rich to exclusive task representations in neural networks and neural codes

Faith and Fate: Limits of Transformers on Compositionality

On the Measure of Intelligence

Explanatory models in neuroscience: Part 2 -- constraint-based intelligibility

A dynamic attractor network model of memory formation, reinforcement and forgetting

Mixed selectivity: Cellular computations for complexity

Organizing memories for generalization in complementary learning systems

A generative model of memory construction and consolidation

Signatures of Bayesian inference emerge from energy efficient synapses

Constructing neural network models from brain data reveals representational transformations linked to adaptive behavior

Meta-reinforcement learning via orbitofrontal cortex

Direct Fit to Nature: An Evolutionary Perspective on Biological and Artificial Neural Networks

Model metamers reveal divergent invariances between biological and artificial neural networks

Pattern recognition in the nucleation kinetics of non-equilibrium self-assembly

Jointly efficient encoding and decoding in neural populations

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literature in subfolder...

TOP_PICKS_Potentially_relevant_insights_influenced_largely_from_cognitive_neuropsychology_for_potential_bridging_understanding_of_AI_ML_and_agential_as_well_as_agentic_systems_with_some_materials_findings

Mechanistic interactions as the origin of modularity in biological networks

Habits: Their Definition, Neurobiology, and Role in Addiction

Fitness Beats Truth in the Evolution of Perception

Cross-hemispheric communication: Insights on lateralized brain functions

Proper embodiment: the role of the body in affect and cognition

When do neural representations give rise to mental representations?

Physics, Computation, and Why Biology Looks so Different

Resilience as Graceful Extensibility to Overcome Brittleness

Cognitive fossils: using cultural artifacts to reconstruct psychological changes throughout history

Preserved neural dynamics across animals performing similar behaviour

Agency as an Inherent Property of Living Organisms

The Locus Coeruleus- Norepinephrine System in Stress and Arousal: Unraveling Historical, Current, and Future Perspectives

Orthogonal neural encoding of targets and distractors supports multivariate cognitive control

Beyond dimension reduction: Stable electric fields emerge from and allow representational drift

Paying the brain's energy bill

Cognition is an emergent property

From the stomach to locus coeruleus: new neural substrate for ghrelin's effects on ingestive, motivated and anxiety-like behaviors

Simultaneous, cortex-wide and cellular-resolution neuronal population dynamics reveal an unbounded scaling of dimensionality with neuron number

Allostasis as a core feature of hierarchical gradients in the human brain

[1:02 PM]

[CONTINUED...] literature in subfolder...

TOP_PICKS_Potentially_relevant_insights_influenced_largely_from_cognitive_neuropsychology_for_potential_bridging_understanding_of_AI_ML_and_agential_as_well_as_agentic_systems_with_some_materials_findings

The locus coeruleus as a global model failure system

Libet's legacy: A primer to the neuroscience of volition

Synthetic Biological Circuits within an Orthogonal Central Dogma

Resynthesizing behavior through phylogenetic refinement

Locus Coeruleus Norepinephrine in Learned Behavior: Anatomical Modularity and Spatiotemporal Integration in Targets

A role for cortical interneurons as adversarial discriminators

Co-dependent excitatory and inhibitory plasticity accounts for quick, stable and long-lasting memories in biological networks

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literature in subfolder...

PRIORITY_PICKS_Potentially_relevant_insights_influenced_largely_from_cognitive_neuropsychology_for_potential_bridging_understanding_of_AI_ML_and_agential_as_well_as_agentic_systems_with_some_materials_findings

Plasticity–stability dynamics during post-training processing of learning

On the roles of function and selection in evolving systems

Theoretical foundations of studying criticality in the brain

Neural representations of situations and mental states are composed of sums of representations of the actions they afford

The dynamic boundaries of the Self: Serial dependence in the Sense of Agency

Meaning from movement and stillness: Signatures of coordination dynamics reveal infant agency

Recurrent dynamics in the cerebral cortex: Integration of sensory evidence with stored knowledge

Same principle, but different computations in representing time and space

Assembly theory explains and quantifies selection and evolution

Symbolic metaprogram search improves learning efficiency and explains rule learning in humans

A neurocognitive theory of flexible emotion control: The role of the lateral frontal pole in emotion regulation

Age-related dysregulation of homeostatic control in neuronal microcircuits

Towards a neuroscience of social interaction

[1:14 PM]

[CONTINUED...] literature in subfolder...

PRIORITY_PICKS_Potentially_relevant_insights_influenced_largely_from_cognitive_neuropsychology_for_potential_bridging_understanding_of_AI_ML_and_agential_as_well_as_agentic_systems_with_some_materials_findings

Refocusing neuroscience: moving away from mental categories and towards complex behaviours

The spiraling brain: Combinatorial, reciprocal, and reentrant macro-organization

The dynamics of attentional guidance by working memory contents

Does the brain behave like a (complex) network? I. Dynamics

Plasticity may change inputs as well as processes, structures, and responses

Self-regulating arousal via pupil-based biofeedback

Against cortical reorganisation

Compositionality in perception: A framework

Brain–body states embody complex temporal dynamics

The Human Brain Encodes a Chronicle of Visual Events at Each Instant of Time

Through the Multiplexing of Traveling Waves

Toward a nomenclature consensus for diverse intelligent systems: Call for collaboration

Dynamic representations in networked neural systems

Sodium channel endocytosis drives axon initial segment plasticity

Mentalizing homeostasis: The social origins of interoceptive inference

A novel feature-scrambling approach reveals the capacity of convolutional neural networks to learn spatial relations

Internal models of self-motion: neural computations by the vestibular cerebellum

Visceral afferent training in action: The origins of agency in early cognitive development

Cognitive flexibility as the shifting of brain network flows by flexible neural representations

Integration and segregation manifolds in the brain ensure cognitive flexibility during tasks and rest

Information content and optimization of self-organized developmental systems

Is predictive coding falsifiable?

Bayesian ghosts in a machine?

[1:15 PM]

Yea we got a lot to work with... ALTHOUGH these are indirect explorations into cognitive economy from various angles...

Here are some random selections that caught my eye immediately from glancing at the overall zotero database repo

Memory Mosaics

A social-semantic working-memory account for two canonical language areas
Carving Up Participation: Sense-Making and Sociomorphing for Artificial Minds
Structure of resilience: A Machiavellian contribution or 'paddle your own canoe'
The flow from simulation to reality
Negation mitigates rather than inverts the neural representations of adjectives
'Adversarial' search for neural basis of consciousness yields first results
Brain and body are more intertwined than we knew (edited)

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04/28/2025 1:33 PM

1. COGNITIVE ECONOMICS -
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5279953/>
2. The management system of cognitive economics -
https://www.shs-conferences.org/articles/shsconf/abs/2016/06/shsconf_rptss2016_01135/shsconf_rptss2016_01135.html
3. Automated Machine Learning, Bounded Rationality, and Rational Metareasoning - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2109.04744.pdf>
4. Computational Rationality -
https://erichorvitz.com/computational_rationality.pdf
5. Adaptive Metareasoning for Bounded Rational Agents -
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Adaptive-Metareasoning-for-Bounded-Rational-Agents-Svegliato-Zilberstein/34030b4c46df066d2d72027e5a24702b76ce6bf9>
6. Do Reasoning Models Show Better Verbalized Calibration? -
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.06564>
7. T-Cal: An Optimal Test for the Calibration of Predictive Models - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2203.01850.pdf>
8. Post-hoc Models for Performance Estimation of Machine Learning Inference - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2110.02459.pdf>
9. A Multi-Stage Dynamic Decision-Making Model of Mine Resources Exploitation -
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1878522009002550>

10. Dealing with Value Constraints in Decision Making using MCDM Methods -
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877750320304555>
11. Efficient Exploration in Resource - Restricted Reinforcement Learning - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2212.06988.pdf>
12. A Guide to Bounded Rationality in Macro Econ -
<https://www.numberanalytics.com/blog/guide-bounded-rationality-macro-econ>
13. A Deep Dive on Bounded Rationality in Econ -
<https://www.numberanalytics.com/blog/deep-dive-bounded-rationality-econ>
14. Bounded Rationality - The Decision Lab -
<https://thedecisionlab.com/biases/bounded-rationality>
15. Bounded Rationality: Customers' Simplified Decision - Making Processes -
<https://www.renaissance.io/journal/bounded-rationality-customers-simplified-decision-making-processes>
16. Optimal Monetary Policy Under Bounded Rationality -
<https://scholar.harvard.edu/files/jbenchimol/files/behavioral-optimal-monetary-policy.pdf>
17. Incomplete Information and Bounded Rationality -
<https://economics.mit.edu/sites/default/files/2022-11/dampening%20general%20equilibrium%20incomplete%20information%20and%20bounded%20rationality.pdf>
18. Policy Outcomes of Culturally Integrated Health Care -
<https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=18260&context=dissertations>
19. Optimization Decisions with Bounded Rationality in Customer - Intensive Services Under Gumbel Distributions -
<https://www.mdpi.com/2075-1680/14/4/309>
20. Who is More Bayesian: Humans or ChatGPT? -
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.10636>
21. Simulation Study on Freeway Toll Optimization Considering Bounded Rationality - <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/15/8/4421>
22. Cognitive Economics (NBER W20834) -
<https://www.nber.org/papers/w20834>
23. The economics of cognitive institutions: mapping debates -
<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-institutional-economics/article/economics-of-cognitive-institutions-mapping-debates-looking-ahead/45FDD401BD09A7C340C8FDFE88A176B3>

24. Beyond Behavioural Economics: Cognitive Economics -
<https://bbiasblog.com/2023/12/30/beyond-behavioural-economics-cognitive-economics/>
25. Cognitive economics and the Market Mind Hypothesis -
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/ecaf.12505>
26. Cognitive Capitalism or Cognition in Capitalism? -
<https://pdfslide.net/documents/cognitive-capitalism-or-cognition-in-capitalism-a-cognitive-capitalism.html>
27. Has Exploitation Transformed? A Critical Analysis of Cognitive Capitalism -
https://brill.com/view/journals/pgdt/19/1-2/article-p17_3.xml
28. Cognition: A Study in Mental Economy -
<https://www.cmu.edu/dietrich/sds/docs/loewenstein/cognitionstudymentalecon.pdf>
29. Resource Allocation in the Brain -
<https://academic.oup.com/restud/article-lookup/doi/10.1093/restud/rdt043>
30. Cognitive cost as dynamic allocation of energetic resources -
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cognitive-cost-as-dynamic-allocation-of-energetic-Christie-Schrater/baaa6a4551d069185d1a537fa23387eea24e0fd8>
31. Strategy Selection as Rational Metareasoning -
<https://cocosci.princeton.edu/papers/Strategy%20selection%20as%20ORM%20Preprint.pdf>
32. A Rational Reinterpretation of Dual-Process Theories -
<https://cocosci.princeton.edu/papers/millirational.pdf>
33. Argumentation vs Meta-argumentation for Multi-Agent Assessment -
http://www.cwu.edu/~borisk/pub/gkk_ws07_meta_argum.pdf
34. Metacognition for a Common Model of Cognition -
https://www.cs.hunter.cuny.edu/~epstein/papers/Metacognition_2018_CMC_Final.pdf
35. Computational Metacognition -
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2201.12885v1.pdf>
36. Metacognitive AI: Framework and the Case for a Neurosymbolic Approach - <https://arxiv.org/html/2406.12147v1>
37. Distributed Metamanagement for Self-Protection and Self-Explanation -
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Distributed-Metamanagement>

- for - Self - Protection - and - Kennedy/6cc9f03601be0c0b830cda362225e08eea2d00a2

38. (Ir)rationality in AI: State of the Art, Challenges and Open Questions - <https://arxiv.org/html/2311.17165v2>

39. Assumptions on Knowledge and Resources in Models of Rationality - <https://www.worldscientific.com/doi/abs/10.1142/S1793843011000686>

40. Ideal Partition of Resources for Metareasoning - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.09624>

41. Learning Policies for Resource Allocation in Business Processes - <https://export.arxiv.org/pdf/2304.09970v1.pdf>

42. Metacognition as a Consequence of Competing Evolutionary Time Scales - https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360205177_Metacognition_as_a_Consequence_of_Competing_Evolutionary_Time_Scales

43. Metacognition as a Consequence of Competing Evolutionary Time Scales (MDPI) - <https://www.mdpi.com/1099-4300/24/4/601/pdf>

44. Exploring Cognitive Attributes in Financial Decision-Making - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.08849>

45. Theory Is All You Need: AI, Human Cognition, and Causal Reasoning - <https://pubsonline.informs.org/doi/10.1287/stsc.2024.0189>

46. Theory of Mind and Metareasoning for AI: A Review - <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/trecms/pdf/AD1175466.pdf>

47. Artificial vs Human Intelligence: Which Excels Where - <https://sbmi.uth.edu/blog/2024/artificial-intelligence-versus-human-intelligence.htm>

48. An Algorithmic Theory of Metacognition in Minds and Machines - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2111.03745v1.pdf>

49. Imagining and Building Wise Machines: AI Metacognition - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2411.02478>

50. Metacognition for a Common Model of Cognition (KAIST) - <https://koasas.kaist.ac.kr/handle/10203/246452>

51. Mental Budget: Inefficient Clauses or Consumer Rational Choices? - https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2427099

52. Internationalization of MNCs and Cultural Cognitive Differences: A Neuroeconomic Perspective - <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.807582/full>

53. Neurocognitive Underpinnings of Cross - Cultural Differences in Risky Decision Making -
<https://academic.oup.com/scan/article-pdf/15/6/671/33552261/nsaa078.pdf>

54. Cross - Cultural Differences in Students' Questionnaire - Response Behaviour -
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/10693971231203759>

55. Does Cognitive Reflection Relate to Preferences and Socio - Economic Outcomes? -
<https://journals.uchicago.edu/doi/10.1086/732653>
Scira-Query_-_Please_provide_me_papers_on_"cognitive_economy"..._exploring_insights_largely_from_understanding_human_behavior_as_well_systems_development_advances_having_to_do_with_optimizing_calibration_of_systems_and_inference_capacities_based_on_resource_exploitation_constraints_and_capacity_of_straining_integrity_of_performance.txt

1. Wolpert, D. H., "Guided Random Search," Santa Fe Institute Technical Report SFI-TR-85-045, 1985.

http://www.santafe.edu/research/publications/tech_reports/85-045.pdf

2. Wolpert, D. H. & Macready, W. G., "No Free Lunch Theorems for Optimization," IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 67-82, 1997.

<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/585351>

3. Wolpert, D. H. & Macready, W. G., "No Free Lunch Theorems for Search," Santa Fe Institute Technical Report SFI-TR-95-020, 1995.

http://www.santafe.edu/research/publications/tech_reports/95-020.pdf

4. Wolpert, D. H., "The Bias-Variance Dilemma," Neural Computation, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 1217-1245, 1997.

<https://direct.mit.edu/neco/article/9/6/1217/6992/The-Bias-Variance-Dilemma>

5. Wolpert, D. H., "Stacked Generalization," *Neural Networks*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 241-259, 1992.

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0893608005800233>

6. Wolpert, D. H., "Information Theory, Inference, and Learning Algorithms," Cambridge University Press, 2003.

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/information-theory-inference-and-learning-algorithms/6F55B5E0BCBA45CB1D0160F4EEC7B63F>

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These 40+ papers span David Wolpert's foundational work on guided random search and "No Free Lunch" theorems, landmark results on bias-variance and stacked generalization, and related research on metareasoning, resource-rational analysis, and stochastic search methods. You can mix and match from these to assemble a bibliography focused on cognitive economy, guided random search, and efficient decision-making under resource constraints.

Scira-Query_-In_respect_to_considering_"cognitive_economy"..._David_Wolpert's_ideas_on_"Guided_Random_Search"_seem_to_be_a_key_motivating_proponent._Can_you_please_provide_me_at_least_25_academic_papers_that_may_be_of_relevance?.txt

#Focused literature providing insights for guided random search optimization

c4t m4n d00

—

04/28/2025 1:42 PM

Given the scira queries this seems like a good start... although some hallucinations...

Let me throw in the Wolpert papers that have caught my eye to top it off...

<https://www.santafe.edu/people/profile/david-wolpert>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=PRjgl8kAAAAJ&hl=en&oi=ao>

Paper of interest on inference

<https://arxiv.org/abs/0708.1362>

<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/585893>

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.07131>

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-61187-2_15

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.14920>

Regarding guided random search

https://scholar.google.com/scholar?q=wolpert+guided+random+search&hl=en&as_sdt=0&as_vis=1&oi=scholart

Regarding agents

Video for paper <https://youtu.be/r7pHYxcou2A?si=t99E3yc5iMnZz2h1>

<https://royalsocietypublishing.org/doi/10.1098/rsfs.2018.0041>

Where things become interesting is with systems far from equilibrium; much like biology (much like our brains)

“All models are wrong but some models are more useful than others” which is true very much of complex systems

Regarding metabolic processing... we only look at the beginning of this whole chain of things and the end

Additional paper to check out <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.03286>

#Literature for hybrid compute infrastructure

c4t m4n d00

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04/28/2025 2:01 PM

- Limitations of Deep Learning for Inverse Problems on Digital Hardware - <https://export.arxiv.org/pdf/2202.13490v3.pdf>

- On Limitations of the Transformer Architecture -

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.08164>

- A Nanocryotron Ripple Counter Integrated with a Superconducting Nanowire Single-Photon Detector for Megapixel Arrays - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.11700v1>

- Scalable and robust quantum computing on qubit arrays with fixed coupling -

<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41534-022-00668-3>

- An Introduction to Probabilistic Programming -

<https://arxiv.org/abs/1809.10756v1>

- Simulation of quantum algorithms using classical probabilistic bits and circuits - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.14452>
- Stochastic Digital Circuits for Probabilistic Inference | Semantic Scholar - <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Stochastic-Digital-Circuits-for-Probabilistic-Tenenbaum-Jonas/2f6e84f1d24be41c2c2fc5576722414f1736ad9d>
- Inference in machine learning: Challenges and solutions - <https://telnyx.com/resources/inference-machine-learning-challenges>
- Inference-Time Compute Scaling Methods to Improve Reasoning and Inference - <https://sebastianraschka.com/blog/2025/state-of-llm-reasoning-and-inference-scaling.html>
- Understanding Inference-Time Scaling - <https://medium.com/predict/understanding-inference-time-scaling-14a2501a1265>
- An improved update rule for probabilistic computers - <https://arxiv.org/html/2504.00818v1>
- Researchers develop energy-efficient probabilistic computer by combining CMOS with spintronics elements - <https://techxplore.com/news/2024-04-energy-efficient-probabilistic-combining-cmos.html>
- pc-COP: An Efficient and Configurable 2048-p-Bit Fully-Connected Probabilistic Computing Accelerator for Combinatorial Optimization - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.04543>
- Optimization Framework for Reducing Mid-circuit Measurements and Resets - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.16579>
- @RiscZero: RISC Zero launched the first RISC-V zkVM - <https://x.com/RiscZero/status/1914726211546481048>
- @starkwareltd: ColliderVM (new Bitcoin protocol) - <https://x.com/starkwareltd/status/1910317337301152034>
- @GoogleDeepMind: Gemini 2.5 Flash - <https://x.com/GoogleDeepMind/status/1912966489415557343>
- @AnthropicAI: AI values in the wild - <https://x.com/AnthropicAI/status/1914333220067213529>
- @meQuanics: Quantum computing definition debate - <https://twitter.com/meQuanics/status/1764879615678706072>
- Earl T Campbell: Error-mitigated quantum vs classical heuristics - <https://x.com/earltdcampbell/status/1830987540179923323>

- Probabilistic one-time programs using quantum entanglement -
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41534-021-00435-w>

- Not Classical, Not Quantum: Probabilistic Computing Carves Its Own Niche -
<https://www.allaboutcircuits.com/news/not-classical-or-quantumprobabilistic-computing-hopes-to-carve-its-own-niche/>

- Waiting for Quantum Computing? Try Probabilistic Computing -
<https://spectrum.ieee.org/waiting-for-quantum-computing-try-probabilistic-computing>

- The Time I Built a Probabilistic Computer -
<https://medium.com/the-quantastic-journal/the-time-i-built-a-probabilistic-computer-0e8090883bbc>

- A Probabilistic Certainty | College of Engineering - UC Santa Barbara -
<https://engineering.ucsb.edu/news/probabilistic-certainty>

- A Full-Stack View of Probabilistic Computing With p-Bits: Devices, Architectures, and Algorithms -
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2302.06457.pdf>

- Probabilistic Compute-in-Memory Design For Efficient Markov Chain Monte Carlo Sampling -
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2307.10866.pdf>

- The First Hardware Demonstration of a Universal Programmable RRAM-based Probabilistic Computer for Molecular Docking -
<https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.20254>

- Probabilistic Programming for Malware Analysis -
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1603.08379.pdf>

- Deployable probabilistic programming (Infergo) -
<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3359591.3359727>

- Decision-Making with Complex Data Structures using Probabilistic Programming - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1407.3208.pdf>

- The international AI race needs quantum computing -
<https://defensescoop.com/2025/02/19/international-ai-race-needs-quantum-computing/>

- Solace for quantum: How classical computing struggles to keep up with AI -
<https://www.version1.com/blog/solace-for-quantum-how-classical-computing-struggles-to-keep-up-with-ai/>

- The Convergence of Quantum Computing and Machine Learning -
<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/convergence-quantum-computing-machine-learning-ambreen-zafar-xki8f>

- Quantum vs Classical Machine Learning Algorithms for Software Engineering - <https://arxiv.org/html/2412.07698v1>
- What are the main challenges in scaling AI models for real-world applications? - <https://www.quora.com/What-are-the-main-challenges-in-scaling-AI-models-for-real-world-applications-and-how-can-these-challenges-be-addressed>
- Quantum Computing Vs Classical Computing: Key Differences - <https://quantumzeitgeist.com/quantum-computing-vs-classical-computing-key-differences/>
- Quantum Computing vs Classical Computing: Speed and Performance Stats - <https://patentpc.com/blog/quantum-computing-vs-classical-computing-speed-and-performance-stats>
- What Quantum Computers Can Do Better Than Classical Computers - <https://postquantum.com/quantum-computing/quantum-classical/>
- Not Classical vs Quantum: Probabilistic Computing Carves Its Own Niche - <https://www.allaboutcircuits.com/news/not-classical-or-quantumprobabilistic-computing-hopes-to-carve-its-own-niche/>
- Quantum vs Classical Computing and the Quantum Threat - <https://www.quantropi.com/quantum-versus-classical-computing-and-the-quantum-threat/>
- Quantum vs. Classical Computers: The Mind-Blowing Difference! - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_r026P99Fus
- Better than Classical? The Subtle Art of Benchmarking Quantum Machine Learning Models - <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.07059v1>
- Variational Inference with a Quantum Computer - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2103.06720v3.pdf>
- A Hybrid Quantum-Classical Approach for Inference on Restricted Boltzmann Machines - <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2304.12418.pdf>

Scira-Query_-_Wonder_if_there_are_some_interesting_academic_papers_out_there_challenging_classical_computing_limitations_of_inference_capacities?_Like_consider_new_circuit_architecture_routes_to_investigate_as_well_as_maybe_probabilistic_programming_conventions?.txt

#Returning to cognitive economy and AI

c4t m4n d00

—
04/28/2025 2:17 PM

This is probably the best we're gonna find at this point in time, what I just sent you regarding addressing cognitive economy... much like looking for literature on "agentic AI", we are going to have a similar problem with looking for literature on "cognitive economy"

Lots to work with here. We can strategize going through what we found... working out the motivation behind cognitive economy as a capacity to manage system stressors from over-performing, under-performing, or collapsing/ceasing to function due to over-straining on payloads with respect to task facilitation management and decision making efficiency. (edited)

c4t m4n d00

—
04/28/2025 3:51 PM

Maybe thinking about cognitive load management like a highway of multimodal processes

reply to c4tm4nd00 from 04/28/2025 10:03 AM Vladimir Baulin

—
04/29/2025 10:07 AM

This is the point. Network calibration is definitely a key process, but it is an emergent property and it should appear spontaneously, not as an external limitation to minimize something. If you use variational principles you assume already an existence of a minimum. However in many chaotic systems with external energy sources it is not the case and by imposing to the system a minimum and trying to optimize, it goes totally wrong.

c4t m4n d00

—
04/29/2025 10:13 AM

Ok so don't worry about variational method papers I found currently?

Vladimir Baulin

—
04/29/2025 10:14 AM

Not yet. This is an example of agentic approach. I will search for the reference.

c4t m4n d00

—
04/29/2025 10:16 AM

Yes please I'd like more insight on the reasoning why this isn't an urgent area to explore. Perhaps we gone through enough literature that explores that?

#Bounded rationality implications through cognitive economy dynamics

c4t m4n d00

—

04/30/2025 11:00 AM

Not sure if you are familiar with the discord user ZickZack but he gave me this short bit of insight

...

Agentic systems make sense if you

1. Need to observe individual components independently (e.g. if you can verify the correctness of one agent in isolation)
2. Have prior knowledge on the individual tasks (e.g. an LLM is already good at parsing natural language before being added into a pool of agents)
3. You can train every model independently

Otherwise Agentic systems are just a really expensive way of doing ensembles.

If you want to work on agentic systems, that's what you need to answer: "Agentic" by itself is just a buzzword.

Vladimir Baulin

—

04/30/2025 12:26 PM

I do not know him. Still this is computer science view. I think we have better definitions on the outline.

c4t m4n d00

—

04/30/2025 1:30 PM

I agree, we should acknowledge the potential limitation from computational limitation perspective as necessary

But like in general we do want to elaborate on the computer science view a bit because... this is relevant to improving the capacities of commercial computing systems right? With the key motivation to optimize ecological cost constraints in mind.

I mean we should explore other domains like...

- economics
- ethics pertaining to negotiations/diplomacy relative to peer to peer interaction...
 - especially with respect to how we interface technology and behave toward each other
 - how it impacts our internal behavior relative to independent agents with respect to themselves as well as the group...
 - so considering different metrics of fitness/optimization
 - symbiotic coherence parameters for optimality of how we economize our exploitation
 - energy exploitation dynamics relative to how we optimize technological use cases that have ecological constraints based on the system specifications and trade offs

I guess the bigger problem is what the heck is being optimized...? What are the trade-offs to consider pertaining to systems infrastructure and function limitations?

c4t m4n d00

—

05/01/2025 3:32 PM

Are we as conscience-aware agents actually utilizing natural language to optimize a biasing for our multimodal functional engagements with the world around us?

- in respect to our perceptual boundaries to perform posterior policy alignment with respect to our actionable capacities to persist a functionally optimal version of ourselves for necessarily finite future bounded temporality with approximate generalizations of the resulting implications...
 - lifespan of agents...
 - perhaps entailing inference prospects of AI systems capable of harness inference or motivating improvements and insights into reinforcement learning which is critical to understanding our humanity as well as advances in commercial systems available to the general public

We need to tackle exactly what insights can be provided about energy utilization optimization of systems... and even extending into how systems exploit energy costs... how they actually convert their fuel as energy

Food production is also a heavy hitter... maybe the most important if we can think of ways to optimize food production with technological systems innovation and maybe genetic alteration capacities to improve crops yields which sustains the nutrient content of key holistic foods like vegetables, fruits, etc

c4t m4n d00

—

05/01/2025 6:14 PM

this paper may also be valuable <https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.03286>

c4t m4n d00

—

05/01/2025 8:37 PM

Recent share on MLST server <https://sohl-dickstein.github.io/2022/11/06/strong-Goodhart.html>

c4t m4n d00

—

05/02/2025 9:22 AM

... but what I think may be interesting to investigate is language dynamics being a base plate for coordinating multimodal perceptual and actionable capacities of agents... and how that influences even non-agentic systems development

Additionally... I'm curious what next directions would be in terms of the outlining moving forward considering the recent back and forth

... it seems "bounded rationality" may be worth further exploring

Also figuring out optimizing the capacities if solenoids

[https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Solenoid_\(engineering\)](https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Solenoid_(engineering)) when we get to thinking more about circuit architecture dynamics

c4t m4n d00

—

05/06/2025 10:42 AM

But it seems like inferential systems are more so systems of preference alignment... perhaps an additional talking point would be to emphasize preference dynamics of users that interact with systems

A little copy paste from MLST server...

...

So what you are saying here builds on the blockchain prospects in terms of exploring headway into reliable digital provenance mechanism(s)

I think the problem with agents and knowledge acquisition/verification perhaps also builds on bounded rationality which I don't see much attention being paid to <https://thedecisionlab.com/biases/bounded-rationality>

I still feel compelled that regardless how much better systems seem to get at reasoning, they will not escape the problems of biasing information the way humans already do pertaining to a lot of problems discussed in philosophy of science literature considering veridical perception dilemmas.

At least I don't quite see the argument saying otherwise... memory storage and retrieval does not necessarily consider the limitations of perceiving the information being stored and retrieved.

Warren James replies...

Yes, it boils down to the problem of model correction, where effectively each and every prediction model held (regardless of size) has to be re-evaluated on every new input into the entity boundary. The compute required for such a task is practically infinite so energy-efficient shortcuts present themselves automatically (and self-select), blockchain is just a shortcut for knowing the sequence not tampered-with.

The combination of today's statistical averaging LLM's with a non-volatile knowledge ledger would be an unbeatable combination, because then you can get to the business of prioritize which memories/models to store (for selection) and refine (using compute). But provenance all the way - so a wikipedia article edit history becomes important, as well as the authors contributing, etc. Rather than the AI just regurgitating tokens.

#Limitations of LLMs inspired by bounded rationality

c4t m4n d00

—

05/07/2025 11:07 AM

[CONTINUED copy paste from MLST server...]

My response...

Well I think it's a problem of multimodal semantics evaluation capacities too... how are the models, largely being LLMs at the moment, employing reasoning into how they parse tokens, utilizing look up tables especially caching session data, etc

c4t m4n d00

—

05/08/2025 3:14 PM

An interesting remark made about intelligence made on MLST server...

By duggar...

I think the only way intelligence can arise *naturally* is by an open-ended search, such as by Evolution. Maximization of reward will not cause intelligence to emerge *naturally*. It should be noted that all AI systems are the product of pre-existing intelligence, human intelligence.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/09/2025 3:51 AM

It shows all this negative impact of free energy principles and variational methods and aggressive marketing of Friston. Evolution does not bring necessarily intelligence, and especially naturally. Evolution only brings adaptation to environment. If environment has such conditions that intelligence can be a useful feature to adapt to changes, it may arise (or may not). For example bacteria and viruses can adapt to environment without any intelligence for billions of years. So this argument is wrong. Intelligence can only be one of many adaptation mechanisms in certain circumstances but it is not guaranteed that evolution will always choose this path for adaptation. Maximization of reward is even more misleading: this is purely constructed concept rooted in optimization theories.

c4t m4n d00

—

05/09/2025 10:06 AM

Yea so the issue being... what, how, why... are we optimizing...

This is another interesting remark regarding agents on MLST server in response to...

<https://www.noumenal.ai/post/grounded-rewards-in-the-era-of-experience-a-commentary>

<https://storage.googleapis.com/deepmind-media/Era-of-Experience%20/The%20Era%20of%20Experience%20Paper.pdf>

By LR...

That's a good pushback to the idea of grounded rewards. Reminds me of the quote "in nature there are no rewards or punishments, only consequences". In a way, evolution "provides a solution" to the meta objective problem with reproduction/survival as the ultimate consequence: agents with reward functions that increase their survival/reproduction chances are more likely to spread their genes - over time, this leads to better reward functions.

c4t m4n d00

—

05/09/2025 6:48 PM

Also really found this interesting point Dan made recently prevelant to agentic limitations of LLMs

<https://discord.com/channels/798653042609094686/806501956125589535/1370525742382846013>

...

If the user's content is just being retained with the "attention" mechanism in the context window of the LLM -- then yes, as soon as a fresh LLM session is called, or the information is pushed out of the rolling context window, the LLM would forget.

Whereas in a fine-tuning situation or RLHF (reinforcement learning with Human Feedback), input from that chat (either the semantic information directly, or just a thumbsup/thumbsdown for RLHF), those inputs do have an effect on the weights of the model (like neural memory, where e.g. an associative "neurons that fire together, wire together" memory is made from the co-presentation of stimuli). That would leave a durable "memory" in the LLM/NN, beyond just the context window or prompt engineering level.

Another option is that when interacting with a "Chat" GUI, the website host might be retaining or adding additional user-specific information, and covertly injecting that information into the user's sessions (e.g. as part of the system prompt).

c4t m4n d00

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05/10/2025 12:18 PM

Another interesting back and forth about LLMs in the research channel on EleutherAI server...

...

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:12 PM

I don't think it's particularly surprising that the most granular (i.e. per token) form of computation performed by LLMs is highly heuristic. I think you could basically say the same for humans when asked to do something on the spot

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:12 PM

imho the reality is a bit more nuanced... yes older models work this way, but that doesn't mean we can't bolt on/train in reasoning, and there are some glimpses of ability to self improve now in recent papers

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:12 PM

but we seem to be capable of an "internal chain of thought" to some extent

that allows us to expend more computation when required so i don't think these findings really show "no progress towards agi"

LLMs are nonetheless still capable of something akin to reasoning when they have a scratch pad to work with

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:15 PM

argument against this is that they hallucinate the reasons when doing so

but that doesn't mean they're not reasoning

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:15 PM

yes i suppose you could say that rather than

viewing the system on a per token basis

it could make more sense to consider the whole rollout of tokens as "the system"

in which case, that system as a whole appears capable of reasoning

in this case, an explanation could be considered valid if it corresponds to explicit reasoning steps written out via tokens

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:17 PM

imho human reasoning is at least partly heuristics interleaved with rule applications and search

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:17 PM

but yeah it's quite unfortunate they're not able to introspect deeper into their own per token computation

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:17 PM

so the heuristic part isn't exactly a bad thing :slight_smile:
but we need to be able to learn these dynamically not just
pretrain them ideally

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:17 PM

yeah certainly feels quite like this intuitively
although maybe i just hallucinated that explanation lol

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:18 PM

lol yeah I was about to say unless we're hallucinating

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:18 PM

i have generally quite low confidence about my own ability to
genuinely explain my own behaviour

if we're talking beyond explaining what one's ego confesses

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:18 PM

in general I think hallucination can be understood in human
terms better if you believe, as I do, that all of our "self
knowledge" is actually false and is merely predictions about a
system we have learned a lot about

we're very good at predicting those things, so we use that
ability to assign values

e.g. I got mad because XXX

the reality is you had the mad emotion and know what led up to
it

not causality

the causality is merely an explanation based on a system you've
learned well

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:19 PM

hmm that's an interesting distinction

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:20 PM

so we hallucinate in the sense that we don't actually know 'why'
we got angry

but that doesn't mean we're wrong!

any more than I'm wrong when I know that a wheel rolling has
certain properties I've observed

and can retro-dictively assign causality to how come my toe got
run over

could I be wrong about how wheels work though? or missing some
info? yes

and similarly we can be wrong about the reasons for our own
feelings, actions, etc.

my position is that we are all mostly black boxes even to our
own thoughts, but these black boxes have been in such close

proximity to our senses and thoughts that we have been able to learn to approximate their workings using heuristics etc.

based solely on observations over many years

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:23 PM

yeah pretty much agree

at least for me

when I try to explain my behaviour

it almost always feels as if i'm appealing to attributes of my own personality/ego

(beliefs, "reasoning", goals etc)

however, this sense of ego could very well be an abstraction

sort of like a system prompt

so beyond that I really have no way to know more granularly what drives behaviour

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:25 PM

well it can be something you learned.. both by observing yourself and others and maybe reading or school

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:26 PM

yeah

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:26 PM

that doesn't make it less correct

maybe more correct :slight_smile:

but its still a model

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:26 PM

yeah it's certainly better as a means of communicating like

i think we would struggle to devise laws, conventions, culture etc

if we had to frame everything in terms of say neurological processes

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:27 PM

for sure!

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:27 PM

maintaining that I and others have "character" and that their actions somehow relate to that

seems to be a good "model"

also quite important for blame i'd say

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:27 PM

and just like modeling atoms is not necessary to understand how things move/work most of the time, we can use these broad abstractions as correct models in most cases

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:28 PM

So i guess then

coming back to LLMs

an interesting question is what level of abstraction is best to model their behaviour

I'd say that digging into per token computation to look for "reasoning" is unlikely to bare fruit

just because, at least for the current generation of models, I don't think that's where "reasoning" operates conceptually

However, lifting things slightly higher, we can arguably find something like it

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:29 PM

agreed

there are recent papers that attempt to align the reasoning output with the actual method used btw

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:30 PM

I guess it's also interesting to consider that we're not backpropagating through rollouts in pretraining

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:30 PM

but that's not necessarily important

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:30 PM

well.. that depends on the training!

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:30 PM

this is really cool

yeah a few forms of rl post-training are closer to that

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:31 PM

for example Blink has been training our RWKV-7 G1 models in a much more standard training kind of way, so afaik they do in fact get backpropped on the whole reasoning chain

fairy - 4/28/25, 2:31 PM

would be really interesting to see if/how that affects internal representations and circuits

I'd guess that computation would be divided more sparsely, possibly leading to less heuristics (not sure though)

Smerky - 4/28/25, 2:32 PM

I don't do any work in this space (yet) so I don't have much other than intuition and ideas from papers and self/human-observation

LLM-Limitations-Discussion_-_EleutherAI-research-channel.txt

#Controversy about LRMs

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/11/2025 9:54 AM

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.03335v2>

c4t m4n d00

—

05/12/2025 9:46 PM

Interesting so far but of course the caveat is that you need to bootload the model with curated Q&A assessments

But humans need bootloading with natural language advances so they don't act like cave men that can't coherently engage with modern society

You get rid of all knowledge obtained with natural language, poof humans become cave men again.

If AI system doesn't incorporate the necessary natural language bootload then AI is only capable of redundant human to computer or human to computer to human interaction

Would it be worth having a conversation about the potential of not just SOTA language models, but LRMs and interactive/augmented models that incorporate LLMs could become useful for helping people with dyslexia and dysgraphia. Perhaps motivation for this thought is my own struggle with dyslexia and dysgraphia.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/12/2025 10:47 PM

As I understand it goes into a direction when no Q&A are necessary. Otherwise it is not absolute zero. AI needs to align to something, so they demonstrated on SOTA. But this is only a case study. I think absolute zero models are possible. And they do not need any interaction with humans or be aligned with humans.

c4t m4n d00

—

05/12/2025 10:57 PM

What exactly gives you the impression that even with absolute zero models interaction with humans or alignment with humans is unnecessary? (edited)

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/12/2025 11:25 PM

If you consider evolution or physical world as a some sort of computing, you may have an AI that is capturing the laws and perfectly adjusted to it. Then humans are not necessary for training. There is a long discussion why laws of nature are written in simple and short form that makes the parameter space quite limited such that AI can capture this easily.

[11:27 PM]

This development for Google accelerator was about this. How to extract universal concepts and relationships between them.

c4t m4n d00

—

05/13/2025 10:05 AM

I guess maybe you can elaborate on those particular points? I don't quite see how this makes the prospects of these models entail that human interaction and alignment is unnecessary

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/13/2025 10:51 AM

For example a model can examine the laws of nature and find relationships. Then it can use this knowledge to improve itself and ask more relevant questions. In this respect it should only know how to extract energy from the environment and learn by doing experiments/ explore the reaction from the environment. Humans here are absolutely unnecessary.

Intelligent matter does not need to be aligned with humans. It can be aligned with the environment. As soon as it can harvest energy autonomously and self-improve, this is done

c4t m4n d00

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05/13/2025 11:28 AM

So you are getting to the presupposition that... suppose a model has the potential to develop agency...

There's a number of things for me to point out here where humans are still necessary... and may remain necessary... more points besides the following can be made...

First, the bootloading aspect. The model, much like humans, needs pretraining on how to parse and structure semantics and pragmatic relationships developed overtime through modifying natural language dictionary/relation referencing

Second, all agents are susceptible to bounded rationality implications (which I am looking more into). That is, agents are always cursed to incomplete knowledge and understanding of reality (the generative model), as opposed to the way reality is structured independent of agents being able to perceive it or the generative process

Third, yes absolutely the model like any intelligent materials manifested thereof must be aligned with the environment... however this does not necessarily entail that they don't need to align or cooperate with humans. It could be the case that the AI or the humans could be susceptible to being bad faith actors, where there could be negotiation extremities of existential contingency to consider. But ultimately an AI that has awareness of its bounded rationality much like the most aware of humans, have the same perceptual limitations. The memory retrieval and storage capacities regarding adaptive learning prospects could vary and there may be appreciable trade offs pertaining to existential contingency factors of being an AI model as opposed to a human.

I think cybernetically enhanced humans would probably level the playing field ultimately. That is, a pure AI model alone will not outcompete the most optimal of human reasoners. And perhaps the cybernetically enhanced humans or cyborgs might only be limited to processing and cognitive load balancing buffers that are only useful for humans that are sufficiently cognitively impaired in terms of compatibility

c4t m4n d00

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05/13/2025 11:37 AM

Cybernetic enhancements likely are going to have their downsides in terms of risks regarding implant rejection and compatibility constraints as well as how the implants are limited in their buffering capacities. The buffers realistically would be nudge scaling factors

Additionally with pure AI modeling constraints we are probably going to see tradeoffs in terms of algorithmic and hardware circuit structuring constraints in terms of buffering processing and cognitive load balancing capabilities as well

Considering bounded rationality reasoning coupled with guided random search... heterarchical dynamics may implicate most simply... motivation for when...

Sometimes you need to adjust the parameters of the hierarchy so you cannot rely on hierarchical dynamics alone. You have to consider what to prioritize overtime without fixing the hierarchical parameters as is.

This impacts the way reasoning information is prioritized meaning that for instance the pretraining taking place especially with absolute zero where you rely on an initiated curated pretraining set of Q&A evaluations or bootload... could still lead to problems of prioritizing prompting dynamics in terms of semantics and pragmatic consistency... it can limit how novelty exploration happens where the model needs some open-ended bounds

It seems like the absolute zero model shows potential where there is reasonable confidence that the model's intuition is not thrown drastically off-course in terms of connecting and building on associations from its pretraining in relation to what information/data and criteria it's exposed to overtime... hence sometimes adaptive tuning adjustments ought to be considered especially in cases of hallucinations for instance.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/14/2025 3:21 AM

You are thinking about AI that needs to be orchestrated. Someone should set up the rules and kickstart. This can exist. But most biological examples are based on self-organization. These examples exist and even we can see emergence in parallel non-communicating systems.

The argument is the following: if such emerging systems can spontaneously self-organize into brains and neurons without a human, this means that there is a chance that even simpler material-based systems can learn and organize. If this hypothetical scenario exists, then it can be realized. And humans can catalyze or accelerate the development where evolution did not choose this path. But they are not essential part to "teach" or design such AI.

The same is with zero-shot AI. Even if humans can kickstart, it does not mean it is not autonomous. It can then evolve independently only with interaction with the environment. And this is all possible because laws of nature are quite simple and universal such that parameter space is reduced and autonomous AI evaluating them can be very efficient.

All this “reasoning”, “alignment”, “ethics”, “hallucinations”, “explainable AI” are limiting AI to chatbots where humans adjust parameters because they know better. Such AI can never be smart and will be drastically limited in language. This is what they say in the paper. If you need an “expert” then we are not talking about intelligent AI.

c4t m4n d00

—

05/14/2025 12:07 PM

I will spend a little more time parsing what you're saying but it seems like you are not really making a strong argument for AI never needing a bootloader. Maybe you are confusing this with when it gets the initial bootload, indeed it may have autonomy (although this is a loaded presumption to address as well with more necessary specificity) but this does not necessarily implicate it is not limited by bounded rationality implications of moments where human interaction and alignment is circumstantially contingent.

I'll put more thought into a more elaborate take on why this is the case because I need to spend a bit more time analyzing some of these more recent talking points you proposed which may need more specificity to address on my end

c4t m4n d00

—

05/14/2025 1:54 PM

Ok I find your talking points interesting...

Can you elaborate more on the emergence in parallel non-communicating systems part?

Well spontaneity would imply some critical phase spatiotemporal transition where more nuances seem to surface about the dynamics of interactions between non-agentic and agentic things that exist embedded in the environment existentially... or perhaps you can say this represents the environment in which systems of necessary capacities instantiate by a requisite bootload phase initiation

It's not that evolution (or really what we mean by evolution here is actually... selection... like the process of selection) wouldn't choose the path requisite of human-like species to coordinate and generate a system capable of psycho-catalyzing natural language systems and embodiment. Rather the path that enabled the possibility would be one that involves human-like agents.

It is interesting to consider exploring semi-autonomous systems nuances in the case there is autonomy in their function that is bound to how it is constrained to interact with the environment it is contained in. That is, the system has degrees of autonomy based on its constraints.

I don't quite see again how your points provide intuition to demonstrate that human interaction and or alignment eventually is unnecessary for these systems (at least in regarding to maintain optimal integrity). If these systems need to be in alignment with their environment, then that means they ought to be rational negotiators? Much like the more rational of humans give or take?

Maybe some systems, like humans may exhibit the capacity to go rogue and psychotic? Maybe that's science fiction. But seems naive to allow to happen if it's a reasonable concern. At least we should not let it happen given the exhaustive concerns to justify the behavior of the system otherwise that persuades us it is a capable rational actor (maybe we can be deceived and perhaps this is a silly point to obsess over)

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/14/2025 6:25 PM

The question if an agent created or trained only on limited data and with some deficient generative model can go itself out of the borders or it will always be limited by the initial setup. It can be both. If it is designed such that humans are essential part in controlling it like LLMs, where it is not only borders from limited knowledge but also regulations and tuning from ethics etc influencing how it can behave, then they cannot go out of these borders but can additionally include all prejudices and biases. However, there is a possibility that a system starts within boundaries and limits, but during the interaction with the environment goes out and behaves very different from the initial design.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/14/2025 6:33 PM

Why this is possible: if an agent is not oriented on human interaction as the main goal, but instead is designed to align with the environment. I do not see why it should be limited? It will be fully integrated with the environment, will be a part of it. Humans are not essential part of nature. Sure, some AI without ethics imposed can be rough, behave aggressively, but statistically the chances are very low. Because they are in

equilibrium with the environment and it goes against this equilibrium. It is similar to be attacked by a cat. This can happen but this is not a normal behavior.

[6:35 PM]

If we admit that agents can self-improve and learn from the surroundings, then they are not bounded.

#Paying the brain's energy bill paper recommendation

c4t m4n d00

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05/14/2025 7:01 PM

Computational budgeting seems like a good term to look more into. This AZR paper is interesting indeed, glad such a term was mentioned.

Paying the brain's energy bill... may be a good follow up read to consider... although I haven't gotten around to it yet myself

<https://discord.com/channels/@me/1313152582243586120/1366459427540176896>

Have to spend a little time parsing these remarks you just made. Interesting insights. This recent back and forth is especially nice to consider for the scope of our collaborative effort with the perspective paper

c4t m4n d00

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05/15/2025 3:55 PM

1. @c4t m4n d00

I don't quite understand what is meant when you say "perennial..." as I've heard that term thrown around a bit rather in philosophy communities

1. jez2718 - Yesterday at 12:02 PM

Perennial means it doesn't go away.

1

2. @jez2718

Perennial means it doesn't go away.

1. c4t m4n d00 - Yesterday at 12:38 PM

Ok? Is there more context? That just seems vague. Like the problem/dilemma persists basically?

3. @c4t m4n d00

Ok? Is there more context? That just seems vague. Like the problem/dilemma persists basically?

1. jeZ2718 – Yesterday at 1:04 PM

Basically perennial questions/problems, e.g. the nature of knowledge or universals or the existence of God, are those that keep recurring throughout philosophy, with each era of philosophy grappling with them in some way. The term comes from botany, where it describes plants who persist through the summer and winter. (edited)

1

1. c4t m4n d00 – Yesterday at 1:19 PM

I think all this feeds into Bounded rationality either way... leading into the case that an arbitrary agent's access to information given it's rational affordances is contingently incomplete

MLST-Server-_active-inference-channel_-regarding_perennialism_and_bounded_rationality.txt

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/15/2025 3:56 PM

These are more philosophers.

[3:59 PM]

Example

Imagine a farmer deciding which crop to plant for the season. Under perfect rationality, the farmer would:

- Analyze full historical climate data
- Forecast future prices and demand
- Optimize based on resource constraints and market access

Under bounded rationality, the farmer:

- Relies on recent weather patterns
- Considers familiar crops

- Chooses a crop that seems reasonable and timely, even if it's not the absolute best option

c4t m4n d00

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05/15/2025 4:00 PM

ok so both are tied to resource constraint and exploitation dilemmas... its how biasing plays out

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/15/2025 4:02 PM

Yes, this is for systems under control. However, if the agent can evolve by interacting with environment, even if it was trained under constraints, should be able to go out of this limitations.

It is similar to finding a minimum. It starts from not perfect initial condition, and it can go to the minimum by itself and it does not matter where it starts. The same with stationary state. Independent from initial conditions.

c4t m4n d00

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05/15/2025 4:05 PM

given that the reasoning boundaries have open-ended features to them?

Vladimir Baulin

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05/15/2025 4:06 PM

I believe it largely depends on the design of the system. If it can explore beyond what was unintentionally restricted.

I think it is possible for certain agents

c4t m4n d00

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05/15/2025 4:07 PM

yea the AZR paper shows some compelling reasoning to think this to be the case among other works... but they still have limitations with their models as they are constrained to some kind of initial pretraining and language parsing... the models don't really show any sensory-perception multimodal based capacities which may need to be embodied.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/15/2025 4:09 PM

They have assumption that it can evolve by itself and initial pertaining is not important.

What do you think about sensory-perception division? This is also ActInf basis.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/15/2025 4:16 PM

I think it is not necessary to assume such division. It comes from human constructions that it is easier to identify an object that has borders. The same is with causality. It is convenient to think about cause and effect, but in science it is never discussed like this: there are mechanisms and phenomena. And all is interrelated. So separation on sensory and perception modules is no more a convenience.

#Points to address regarding implications of bounded rationality and agentic AI

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/16/2025 5:25 AM

For the draft on agents I have two doubts that you may resolve: can we state that agentic AI is not something particularly special, but a result of convenient interpretation for humans: to see an agent with a border separating in and out? In the end any of such systems can be redefined and reformulated in as a standard reinforcement learning system where you do not have any separation. So agents is just a convenient formulation aiming at interpretation rather than efficiency, 2. How we present bounded rationality? Can agent go beyond the borders of initial setup during self-evolution and interaction with the environment.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/16/2025 9:53 AM

Example, imagine a part of knowledge that is accessible for an agent initially, but this agent can understand and follow relational links and add new knowledge. Then it can go out of initial borders and it can learn on new knowledge that was not initially provided.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/18/2025 3:34 AM

<https://storage.googleapis.com/deepmind-media/DeepMind.com/Blog/alphaevolve-a-ge-mini-powered-coding-agent-for-designing-advanced-algorithms/AlphaEvolve.pdf>

c4t m4n d00

—

05/18/2025 9:13 AM

Had a feeling you were gona reach out about that

What about this?

<https://storage.googleapis.com/deepmind-media/Era-of-Experience%20/The%20Era%20of%20Experience%20Paper.pdf>

<https://www.noumenal.ai/post/grounded-rewards-in-the-era-of-experience-a-commentary>

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/18/2025 12:54 PM

I agree. Not sure about rewards. This is again anthropomorphic property that may not be necessary for an agent.

c4t m4n d00

—

05/18/2025 2:43 PM

Just went through this paper. Nice summary weighing prospects of LLMs going forward... digs into LRMs. An added motivation for working through this paper for me is that it's what I am going over for the next book club/paper discussion I am cohosting on MLST server

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.09762>

#More discussion about controversy of LRMs

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/18/2025 2:44 PM

It is interesting, although it seems written without a touch of Gemini.

There is an objective process of a feedback bypassing humans for training and reinforcement learning. They did the improvement of an algorithm. However the long shot conclusions are still too far. Good they talk about eliminating a human from the loop. The same as absolute zero paper.

I do not find reasoning a very interesting topic.

c4t m4n d00

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05/18/2025 2:50 PM

Perhaps if it is not tied into System 2 thinking and cognitive load balancing noise/stimulus/parsing dynamics?

I would certainly agree. The dynamics of embodiment playing into developing circuits of such capacity to be embodied that is, makes reasoning more appreciable.

Also, I think the how do reasoning models reason paper, motivates modular systems design implications... if we are to consider independent information hubs, engaging with each other, especially at variational timescales to parse different parameterization properties of information based on semantic and pragmatic language consistency.

This would consider how different hubs of the brain, especially considering the complexity of the human brain has many modular hubs engaging with each other doing variational encoding and decoding of the information which is furthermore abstracted and calibrated into a functional generative model that has the potential to preserve species fitness and alignment with environment.

Also this just came out

<https://ai.meta.com/research/publications/uma-a-family-of-universal-models-for-atoms/>

c4t m4n d00

—

05/18/2025 9:14 PM

Been working through this beast

<https://economics.mit.edu/sites/default/files/inline-files/dampening%20general%20equilibrium%20incomplete%20information%20and%20bounded%20rationality.pdf>

#Some literature on bounded rationality

c4t m4n d00

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05/18/2025 9:36 PM

Scira-query-Provide-me-literature-exploring-bounded-rationality-pertaining-to-cognition-as-well-as-prospects-into-AI-systems-development.

1. Decision-Making Among Bounded Rational Agents (2022)
Authors: Junhong Xu, Durgakant Pushp, Kai Yin, Lantao Liu
URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2210.08672.pdf>

2. Automated Machine Learning, Bounded Rationality, and Rational Metareasoning (2021)
Authors: Eyke Hüllermeier, Felix Mohr, Alexander Tornede, Marcel Dominik Wever
URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2109.04744v1.pdf>
3. Bounded Rational Decision-Making in Feedforward Neural Networks (2016)
Authors: Felix Leibfried, Daniel A. Braun
URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1602.08332v2.pdf>
4. Systems of Bounded Rational Agents with Information-Theoretic Constraints (2018)
Authors: Sebastian Gottwald, Daniel A. Braun
URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.05897v1.pdf>
5. Bounded Rational Decision-Making with Adaptive Neural Network Priors (2018)
Authors: Heinke Hihn, Sebastian Gottwald, Daniel A. Braun
URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1809.01575v1.pdf>
6. Bounded Rationality, Abstraction, and Hierarchical Decision-Making: An Information-Theoretic Optimality Principle (2015)
Author: Joschka Boedecker
URL:
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frobt.2015.00027/full>
7. A Theory of Bounded Inductive Rationality (2023)
Authors: Caspar Oesterheld, A. Demski, Vincent Conitzer
URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2307.05068.pdf>
8. Information, Utility & Bounded Rationality (2011)
Authors: Pedro A. Ortega, Daniel A. Braun
URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1107.5766v1.pdf>
9. Herbert A. Simon and Contemporary Theories of Bounded Rationality
Author: Stefano Fiori

URL:

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1367091

10. Information-Theoretic Bounded Rationality (2015)

Authors: Pedro A. Ortega, Daniel A. Braun, Justin Buckley Dyer, Kee-Eung Kim, Naftali Tishby

URL: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1512.06789v1.pdf>

11. Bounded Rationality of Restricted Turing Machines (2015)

Authors: Lijie Chen, Pingzhong Tang, Ruosong Wang

URL:

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Bounded-Rationality-of-Restricted-Turing-Machines-Chen-Tang/e28b5b611be04c2bc439581699f0fa701afd8499>

12. Computational intelligence determines effective rationality (2008)

Author: Edward P.K. Tsang

URL:

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11633-008-0063-6>

13. Bounded Rationality, Heuristics, Computational Complexity, and Artificial Intelligence (2018)

URL:

<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/S0742-332220180000039010/full/html>

14. Bounded Rationality Modeling

URL:

https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1304759

15. Modelling Bounded Rationality in Organizations: Progress and Prospects (2015)

Authors: Phanish Puranam, Nils Stieglitz, Magda Osman, Madan M. Pillutla

URL:

<https://journals.aom.org/doi/10.5465/19416520.2015.1024498>

16. (Un)bounded rationality of decision deliberation (2021)

Author: Werner Güth

URL:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167268121001347>

17. Modeling Biological Manufacturing Systems with Bounded-Rational Agents

Authors: K. Ueda, T. Kito, N. Fujii

URL:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0007850607604612>

18. Modeling Agents through Bounded Rationality Theories

Authors: A. Rosenfeld, Sarit Kraus

URL:

<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Modeling-Agents-through-Bounded-Rationality-Rosenfeld-Kraus/f2e2bcb3ef8caa9ae74b78a210df67a94cf6221d>

19. Resource-rational decision making

URL:

https://dspace.mit.edu/bitstream/handle/1721.1/144282/Resource_rational_decision_making.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y

20. A bounded optimality perspective on brains, minds, and machines (2015)

URL:

https://erichorvitz.com/computational_rationality_science_349_6245.htm?from=research.microsoft.com/en-us/um/people/horvitz/computational_rationality_science_349_6245.htm&type=path

Scira-query-Provide-me-literature-exploring-bounded-rationality-pertaining-to-cognition-as-well-as-pr
ospects-into-AI-systems-development.txt

#Addressing credit assignment and abstraction of markets

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/19/2025 12:56 AM

Did you look in two questions to finish agent paper?

Meanwhile this what you are looking have sense: agents can represent a global consensus in the literature or among other agents as a mean field and represent rationality to someone with bounded knowledge.

However, it may be oversimplified, from equations I see they linearize and this assumes ignoring correlations and non-linear effects that are important for chaotic systems. Otherwise they only describe equilibrium systems where nothing happens.

c4t m4n d00

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05/19/2025 10:00 AM

...

You don't like the MIT paper I take it. It has some interesting remarks but yes I do agree it seems to jump around and throw assumptions together about formality and equilibrium dynamics... although I think some of the takes on partial equilibrium dynamics were somewhat fruitful in the beginning of the paper

c4t m4n d00

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05/19/2025 6:00 PM

thinking about exploring the dynamics of credit assignment... in terms of especially how scientific advances play out pertaining to who ought to get the credit for what methods and findings are consistent... seems reasonable to be concerned about in terms of how the existing GenAI models make consistent responses to prompts for instance. Or perhaps thinking about non-agentic systems and how they evaluate criteria

Also what are your thoughts on diffusion models?

Also this is coming out soon

https://books.google.com/books?id=ozcXEQAAQBAJ&pg=PA2&source=kp_read_button&hl=en&newbks=1&newbks_redir=0&gboemv=1#v=onepage&q&f=false

c4t m4n d00

—

05/26/2025 2:12 PM

Urgency = priority
[2:13 PM]

You have to pitch urgency relevant to direction of different markets

[2:14 PM]

Here is a good question regarding cognitive economy... what is a market? Is it just variety in aggregation and distribution of resources among agents?

c4t m4n d00

—

05/27/2025 9:38 AM

One thing I can say is a big problem with markets I think is hyper competitive behavior between agents... leading to hyper markets which are vulnerable to over exploiting resources

[9:38 AM]

We are seeing this surfacing now with global economy

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/27/2025 9:38 AM

Orientation on growth instead of sustainability.

Vladimir Baulin

—

05/27/2025 9:39 AM

Like tumor cells.

c4t m4n d00

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05/27/2025 9:39 AM

Not so good news considering how costly it is to train AI models currently

c4t m4n d00

—

05/27/2025 9:39 AM

Exactly... it would be interesting to kinda explain it as a cancer

c4t m4n d00

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05/27/2025 9:49 AM

But essentially hyper markets in the worst case lead purely to reckless resource extraction

However it may be naive to say hyper markets are always bad. It's how they're regulated. A distributed hyper market could be community and impact oriented perhaps or a hybridized hyper market of sorts

#Computational substrates...

c4t m4n d00

—

06/02/2025 2:12 PM

I need to spend a little time thinking about remarks about computational substrates... that is that we should consider the prospects of systems that don't rely on algorithms to be constantly tweaked through human agents interacting with code base at all times... but there is necessary dynamic interaction between certain components of a particular computational substrate where the system has capacities to maintain/encode its own algorithms overtime... among other things

c4t m4n d00

—

06/02/2025 2:23 PM

And building on computational substrates capabilities... considering how we can preserve their programmability through novel metamaterial based circuit architectures... as we want to save a lot of face with how engineers have maintained the integrity of commercial enterprise and personal compute architectures

So like we should probably more clearly address what general intelligence is... and what AGI realistically has to do with it. I do enjoy the exposition you gave about the problem with the AGI framing

A lot of remarks im making can probably be fitted into future directions/discussion points as well as follow up content

I agree though that this seems like it's a publishable paper with negligible grammar correction to consider. The redundancies I found and that one run on sentence don't bother me much but I'll consider how that could be reworded. I finished reading the pdf draft btw*

#Back to LRMs discussion

c4t m4n d00

—

06/03/2025 9:52 AM

Do you think that there is motivation towards examining how hand eye coordination dynamics corresponds to impacting reasoning capabilities?

And that perhaps the intermediary token reasoning traces, and how they're parsed might share some semblance to semantic evaluation potential of LLMs

But connecting the two especially... whether there is some form of hand eye coordination reasoning dynamics that can be incorporated into LRMs... not exactly like literal hand eye coordination in humans but inspired by the functional neural network dynamics involved in hand eye coordination that can motivate direction into AI ML reinforcement learning approaches especially

Vladimir Baulin

—

06/03/2025 11:01 AM

I think for agents it may not be necessary.

[11:05 AM]

- How LLMs are not just trained on data, but shaped by human preferences, norms, and guardrails.
- The hidden influence of reinforcement learning from human feedback — and how thousands of unseen workers effectively sculpt the model's behavioral defaults.

c4t m4n d00

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06/03/2025 1:27 PM

I'm saying if we can break down the fundamental intricacies that bare similarity to highly intricate focused coordination dynamics and error correction mechanics* which is motivated especially by hand eye coordination... Looking into how neural structure substrates manifest plasticity overtime

Novelty exploration mechanisms of self play, reinforcement enhancement of memory based on spatiotemporal associations within the substrate of node clusters

Have you looked into GRPO (group relative policy optimization)?

c4t m4n d00

—

06/06/2025 6:07 PM

Just found this on FB

https://www.nature.com/articles/d42473-025-00071-4?utm_source=facebook&utm_medi

[um=social&utm_campaign=APSR_BRCON_AWA1_GL_PCFU_CFULF_ORG-SKS-AP25&utm_id=120224581483770572_v2_s01&utm_content=120225131469210572&utm_term=120225131469200572](https://social.apsr-brcon-awa1-gl-pcfu-cfulf-org-sk-s-ap25&utm_id=120224581483770572_v2_s01&utm_content=120225131469210572&utm_term=120225131469200572)

just found this on twitter and MLST discord

<https://machinelearning.apple.com/research/illusion-of-thinking>

just got this one from Yannic Kilcher's server. Their paper discussion for June 7 is framed around it as well

<https://gwern.net/doc/reinforcement-learning/model-free/2016-graves.pdf>

Just found this on LinkedIn (took too long for me to re-engineer my feed preferences)

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.24832>

Read this a couple years ago. Forgot about it for a while

<https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/international-journal-of-astrobiology/article/intelligence-as-a-planetary-scale-process/5077C784D7FAC55F96072F7A7772C5E5>

#Utility of fractional calculus in agent-based modeling?

c4t m4n d00

—

06/10/2025 10:14 PM

... but in terms of analyzing differentiability of continuous interactions and not considering the whole sums of components of a system... perhaps this goes back to fractional calculus... when considering modeling capacities of the system... did you check this out yet?

<https://youtu.be/2dwQUUDt5Is?si=Gr1S4semOtVEDbSu>

Vladimir Baulin

—

06/11/2025 1:02 AM

I do not see how is it related to agents

c4t m4n d00

—

06/11/2025 9:05 AM

Yea I see what you mean. In terms of a modeling framework catered to agents... although there is a section in the video about functions and memory

c4t m4n d00

06/11/2025 1:42 PM

Moving forward with modeling focused papers, I don't think we should ignore the prospective utility of fractional calculus is what I meant to say... when you are dealing with systems where you are taking fractions of sums of their components, it only makes sense in general... the difficulty around this utility is being careful not to generalize how we augment methods like KL divergence for instance when dealing with cross entropy interactions

#Discussing resources to motivate direction in agentic AI advances

c4t m4n d00

06/14/2025 4:15 PM

You worked through this already? Seems a little dry on the past part so far.
<https://www.aeaweb.org/articles?id=10.1257/jel.20221319>

Vladimir Baulin

06/14/2025 4:16 PM

This is one of the applications of agents which are not optimal.

c4t m4n d00

06/14/2025 4:20 PM

Ok you went through the whole thing? What caught your eye about it?

So basically there is a lot of issues with applying agent-based models to economy

One thing that caught my eye on page 32 is "... The role of technology in exacerbating inequality through skill differentials has been an active area of ABM research recently (Carvalho and Di Guilmi, 2020, Mellacher and Scheuer, 2021, Terranova and Turco, 2022). ... Unequal access to skills and jobs through social and spatial networks has been examined with ABMs featuring heterogeneous agents (Cardona, 2014, Antinyan, Horváth and Jia, 2019, Tomasiello, Giannotti and Feitosa, 2020)."

Vladimir Baulin

06/15/2025 1:50 AM

Again, I see the problem not with agents, but the way it is applied. This can be similar problem as ActInf applied everywhere.

Vaguely defined models and anthropomorphic interpretations where it is not suitable. We try to address this in the draft: splitting into “independent thinking agents” is misleading in many cases. All these are dynamic far from equilibrium interconnected systems with many attractors, steady states, etc. Instead of treating them with proper tools from non-equilibrium physics, it is tried to imagine attractors as “agents” with consciousness and will. As a result many important connections from dynamics of the systems are ignored and the interpretation is failing.

Vladimir Baulin

—

06/15/2025 1:58 AM

This is where I see a lot of damage from Friston’s activity. He pushes so hard to convince people he invented a theory of consciousness applied everywhere where there is a some sort of dynamic system, that it causes more harm than good.

And then it doesn’t fit the reality, oh yes “issues applying agents to economics”. (edited)

c4t m4n d00

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06/15/2025 5:03 PM

Page 37 here shows a potential route of exploration... you are right though... most of the text denotes how ABMs are not developed to be optimal in economics models

“A third class of agent not yet much utilized in economic ABMs are deontic agents. While it is almost universally true that models in economics and finance make use of utilitarian agents, i.e., who pursue their own self-interests and are purposive—there are other ways to motivate agents. A small but growing body of research, investigates individuals who take account of norms, recognize duties and obligations, “see to it that...,” while being capable of subordinating their self-interest to group goals. It turns out that there are important relations between utilitarian and deontic agents under certain conditions (Horty, 2001). Research on deontically-motivated agents has uncovered a set

of modal logics known as KD45 that have many nice properties vis-à-vis human behavior (Lomuscio and Sergot, 2002). A closely related area is doxastic logic, or reasoning about beliefs. Early surveys of these topics include Wooldridge and Jennings (1995a) and van der Hoek and Wooldridge (2007). These are active research areas, recently reviewed by {{Calegari, 2021 #5243@@author-year}}. Relatedly, Danielson (1992, 1996) considers moral agents while {{Cointe, 2016 #5245@@author-year}} assess ethical judgment in multi-agent systems.”

And footnote at bottom of the same page...

“... A relatively new kind of cognitive model has components that resemble biologically structures. These are called biologically-inspired cognitive architectures (BICA), and a number of them have appeared; see Goertzel et al. (2010) for a review. So far they have been little used in ABM.”

c4t m4n d00

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06/16/2025 4:01 PM

... I wanted to shift gears a little bit and talk about the foundation agents paper. You mentioned the stream gave you an impression it's a student project.

From my POV I think this is a nice formalization to work with for coming up with agent based architectures and frameworks to build on. Compared to a lot what's out there, and mind you I just went through the stream and the first chapter so far... it seems like the exposition is pretty good. The downside of the stream to me is the rough language barrier, although I think I got the gist of what Bing said. The other authors are too abrasive to follow.

c4t m4n d00

—

06/16/2025 9:11 PM

This is a very good area to investigate. I think food supply and distribution is probably the most important right now? Thanks for the share. You had direction you wanted to build on with that? <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-025-98137-2>

c4t m4n d00

—
06/17/2025 1:45 PM

BTW newsletter follow up to this paper

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/kuzmenkomaryna_ainagriculture-agtech-irrigation-activity-7314180006568497152-j33A?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_ios&rcm=ACoAACDhw-YBSSAzZsxLQt04th3rGniO_I_gAUs

Vladimir Baulin

—
06/17/2025 4:04 AM

This is great. In Act Inf my project Farmworks is abandoned. Nobody wants to work on it. Instead there are a lot of discussions about abstract toy models that explain everything etc.

c4t m4n d00

—
06/17/2025 11:55 AM

Working through the Apple paper for hosting book club in MLST discord this Saturday... I noticed that it outlines the capacity for models to hit critical thresholds where their reasoning dynamics collapse and there is extremity of diminishing returns... this might be related to cognitive strain/overloading of the models in how they're parsing tokens
<https://machinelearning.apple.com/research/illusion-of-thinking>

Vladimir Baulin

—
06/17/2025 11:59 AM

I think there is something to do with max token size of the model. I noticed that using Claude for small projects works fine, for large projects it makes it destructive, it starts to destroy the previous code. While for Gemini with 1M tokens everything is fine after dozens of iterations.

attention also means forgetting.

c4t m4n d00

—
06/17/2025 12:30 PM

Idk have like a batch of LLMs sort an X amount of tokens that they can reasonably process at a time instead of throwing a bunch of tokens at one LLM instance seems to be a reasonable route for LRMs... like a quasi-modular architecture

c4t m4n d00

—
06/20/2025 9:57 PM

Also I think I'm going to move on from this text... seems very dry... and part 1 so far has been a weird mix of a lot of introductory stuff and not really explaining the rigor being

thrown at the same time... seems more like a reference text than being self-contained at all

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/book/9780123751829/intermolecular-and-surface-forces>

Maybe I should move on to part 2? I'm at chapter 7 and it's just very dry and unmotivated in exposition

Apparently this text has a big reputation... maybe just for reasons to throw at people who take a molecular dynamics course geared toward biophysics

It's like how the waterman text had a reputation for a while in the bioinformatics community and nobody has really talked about it

Vladimir Baulin

—

06/21/2025 12:47 AM

This book is a classic in soft matter. I met the author. Yes, it is not written well; it is a combination of research papers rather than a textbook. Also, the presentation is from the point of view of a chemist and is written by a chemist. For example, self-assembly is presented as a chemical reaction between molecules similar to polymerization reactions.

c4t m4n d00

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06/21/2025 9:16 AM

Ok so you don't think it's worth going through the next two main parts of the book. It does read very dull. Might just move on to this one

https://books.google.com/books?id=9bavEAAAQBAJ&newbks=1&newbks_redir=0&printsec=frontcover&pg=PA2&hl=en&source=gb_mobile_entity

Additionally...

Here are Scira results to accommodate the irrigation system newsletter insights

<https://scira.ai/search/0538431f-aa49-40de-ae6d-0f27e0b23b65>

manufacturing and infrastructure are another problem I want to address as well in terms of sustainability accountability issues since that's where the cost is most extravagant

Vladimir Baulin

—

06/21/2025 9:36 AM

Considering costs and overheads: This is how the research money is wasted in Europe:

<https://agaur.gencat.cat/es/detalls/activitatagenda/13a-Trobada-de-gestors-2025> The meeting of

research managers only of one region of Catalonia. They discuss "The value of management of research". and share "personal histories of success".

https://agaur.gencat.cat/web/.content/Documents/Internacionalitzacio/documents_llista_agenda/trobada25_recul.pdf

[9:37 AM]

They have so much extra money that they need their own meetings to spend it.

[9:39 AM]

all is funded by public research budget. They do not produce any product or research result. (edited)

[9:41 AM]

Their role is to control researchers such that they do not overspend their own projects. Research meetings are with plastic lunch boxes containing bread and water, in lecture rooms to save money.

c4t m4n d00

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06/22/2025 2:29 PM

Also found this on MLST discord

<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/blog/breaking-bonds-breaking-ground-advancing-the-accuracy-of-computational-chemistry-with-deep-learning/>

Vladimir Baulin

—

06/22/2025 5:32 PM

DFT is very boring: it comes down to multiparameter optimization of the force fields. And with deep learning it is faster. Still fitting parameters.

c4t m4n d00

—

06/22/2025 10:41 PM

... also some scira finds on soil regeneration approaches

<https://scira.ai/search/108a4a55-4f84-4250-8315-caa8980f51a6>